

Failure Probability Reduction in Vertical Seawalls Using Retrofit Measures: A Probabilistic Approach

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ABSTRACT

Wave overtopping poses a critical challenge for vertical seawalls, particularly under accelerating sea level rise. This study applies empirical overtopping formulas and Monte Carlo Sampling to quantify failure probabilities for seawalls with and without retrofit measures. Results indicate that nature-based solutions such as reefs and vegetation reduce failure probability by up to 23.7%, while optimally designed recurve geometries achieve reductions exceeding 90%. These findings highlight the potential of both ecological and structural retrofits to substantially enhance seawall resilience against overtopping.

Keywords: Seawall, Overtopping, Retrofit, Failure probability, Monte Carlo Sampling

1 INTRODUCTION

Vertical seawalls are widely used for coastal protection, yet overtopping remains a persistent risk, particularly under future sea level rise combined with extreme climatic events. According to the IPCC (2023), climate change is expected to exacerbate overtopping intensity and frequency. Retrofitting seawalls with additional protective measures has emerged as an effective approach to mitigate this risk (Dong et al., 2020; Torabbeigi et al., 2024). This study evaluates the probability of seawall failure due to overtopping beyond permissible thresholds, comparing baseline performance with a range of retrofit options. Empirical formulas were applied within $R_c/H_{m_0} = 1.0-1.3$ to establish a consistent framework for identifying optimal retrofit strategies. A probabilistic framework was employed to capture the uncertainties inherent in empirical overtopping relationships and laboratory-derived parameters. This comparison allows for a reliability-based assessment of retrofit effectiveness, providing insights that can support the optimization of seawall designs under variable hydraulic conditions.

2 METHODOLOGY

This study evaluates the performance of a vertical seawall under baseline and retrofitted conditions, incorporating reefs, vegetation, and recurve geometries. The geometric configurations of the reef, vegetated foreshore, and recurve wall are illustrated in Figure 1 and summarized in Table 1, providing the essential parameters used in the probabilistic analysis. Geometric and hydraulic parameters were selected based on laboratory ranges, with uncertainties quantified according to CEM guidelines (Burcharth, 1997).

Table 1. Geometric and Hydraulic Parameters with Associated Uncertainties

Parameter	Value / Range	COV
Seawall height (m)	12.5	–
h_s (m)	6	0.10
R_c/H_{m_0}	1.00 – 1.30	–
Peak period (s)	10	0.05

Significant wave height (m)	5.0 – 6.5	0.20
B_r (m)	2.0, 3.2, 4.2, 0.8	–
h_r (m)	2.0, 2.5, 0.95	–

Figure 1. Cross-Section of Retrofit Configurations

Calculations were performed using empirical wave overtopping formulas as limit state functions. In this study, all overtopping formulas are in the form of a general widely practiced formula as follows:

$$\frac{q}{\sqrt{gH_{m0}^3}} = a \left(\frac{H_{m0}}{h_s \times S_{m-1,0}} \right)^c \exp \left(b \frac{R_c}{H_{m0}} \right) \quad [1]$$

The coefficients used in the empirical formulas vary depending on the type of structure. For the reef, the coefficients were defined as $a=0.0055$, $c=1$, and $b=-3.15$, with an RMSE of 0.239. For vegetation cover, the corresponding values were $a=0.0053$, $c=1$, and $b=-3.5$, with an RMSE of 0.234. In the case of the vertical seawall, the coefficient a was treated as a random variable with a mean of 0.011 and a standard deviation of 0.0045 (Eurotop, 2018), while $c=0.5$ and $b=-2.2$ were kept constant. For the recurve wall, the overtopping discharge was expressed as a correction of the seawall discharge ($q = k * q_{Seawall}$), with three different formulations:

Kortenhaus et al. (2003) with RMSE = 1.06:

$$k = \begin{cases} 1 & R_c/H_s \leq R_0^* \\ 1 - \frac{1}{m} \left(\frac{R_c}{H_s} - R_0^* \right) & R_0^* < R_c/H_s \leq R_0^* + m^* \\ k_{23} - 0.01 \left(\frac{R_c}{H_s} - R_0^* - m^* \right) & R_c/H_s \geq R_0^* + m^* \end{cases} \quad [2]$$

PEARSON et al. (2004) with RMSE = 0.64:

$$k = \begin{cases} k & R_c/h_s \leq 0.6 \\ k * 180 \exp \left(-8.5 \frac{R_c}{h_s} \right) & 0.6 < R_c/h_s \leq 1.1 \\ 0.02 * k & \frac{R_c}{h_s} > 1.1 \end{cases} \quad [3]$$

Dong et al. (2024) improved the relation proposed by Kortenhaus et al. (2003) by introducing a correction factor α defined as (with RMSE = 0.44):

$$\alpha = 0.056 + 0.00035 \left(\frac{R_c}{H_{m0}} \right)^{-4.8} S_{m-1,0}^{-2.1} \quad [4]$$

Failure probability was estimated using Monte Carlo Sampling, with allowable overtopping limits of $q = 10^{-1} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}/\text{m}$ for reef/vegetation retrofits and $q = 10^{-2} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}/\text{m}$ for recurve walls, treating the "a" coefficient as a probabilistic variable per Eurotop (2018) and incorporating RMSE as standard deviation via a probabilistic multiplier to account for uncertainty in other formulas.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The results in Figure 2-a show that using a reef and vegetation significantly reduces the probability of failure due to overtopping. This reduction varies with the relative freeboard ratio (R_c/H_{m0}), with the greatest reduction occurring at $R_c/H_{m0} = 1.30$ (6.52% and 23.70% for the reef and vegetation, respectively) and the smallest reduction at $R_c/H_{m0} = 1.04$ (0.91% and 12.98%, respectively). This trend confirms the effectiveness of nature-based solutions in enhancing seawall performance under moderate to high freeboard conditions.

The maximum reduction (91.3%) was obtained for $B_r = 2 \text{ m}$ and $h_r = 4.2 \text{ m}$ at $R_c/H_{m0} = 1.3$. However, increasing h_r alone does not always improve performance; the B_r/h_r ratio must be optimized for efficient flow deflection and minimized overtopping. At a given R_c/H_{m0} , the probabilistic comparison demonstrates how each retrofit option decreases failure probability relative to the baseline seawall, providing designers with quantitative insight into the expected reliability gain for each configuration. Furthermore, the probabilistic evaluation of different empirical overtopping relationships for recurve wall geometries revealed that the selection of a specific empirical model can itself influence the resulting failure probability. This highlights that model-based uncertainty can be comparable to geometric variability, reinforcing the importance of model selection within reliability-based coastal design. Overall, the study highlights that both ecological and structural retrofits are viable strategies for improving seawall resilience—recurve walls achieving the largest reliability gains, while nature-based measures offer additional

environmental and multifunctional co-benefits supporting sustainable coastal adaptation.

Figure 2. Probability of failure for seawall and retrofit configurations: (a) recurve wall geometries, (b) reef and vegetation.

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